

A Comparative Study on Secondary Students' Environment Awareness and Achievement in Life Science

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ABSTRACT : There are various kind of environmental pollution against which environmental awareness must be increased among the human beings specially school students of our future prospect for recovering the unbalanced environment. The environmental awareness on water pollution were studied on five dimensions of aspects like knowledge, understanding, causes, remedies and extent of awareness on water pollution. The present study revealed that knowledge on water pollution is the highest percentage of the secondary students in West Bengal. It is also observed that there is a significant difference present between mean of scores of the students of Environmental Awareness and Life Science and a low correlation presents between them.

Keywords : Environmental Education, Environmental Awareness

Introduction

Science as a specified field of knowledge based on facts and data started its journey from the beginning of civilization through a path of time illuminated by discoveries as well as have dark regions hindered by superstitions and dogmas. Due to tremendous knowledge explosion and evolution through gradual discovery in aims and methodology used in scientific investigation, science was broadly

divided into two main disciplines-Physical Science and Biological Science. The subject goal of Biological Science was to help the learner to help not only a better understanding about our living world but also about the relationship with them.

On the other hand the welfare and existence of human race depends upon the proper interaction of **Man** and his **Environment** which play a vital role in the physical and mental health

of a child. So in these respect environmental awareness was needed to reduce the problematic destabilising factors in the field of air, water, land etc. and built a green and clean world (Agarwal, 2006).

Dictionary meaning of awareness is ‘Having Perception’ or knowledge (Sharma, 2007). So educational awareness may be defined as having perception or knowledge about the surrounding physical and biological factors along with their chemical interactions that affect an organism.

“The accomplishment or proficiency of the pupils, particularly that resulting from schooling instructions” (Gerbrich, 1956: Senapati et.al. 2009). “Academic achievement is knowledge attained or skill developed in school subject usually measured by designated test scores or assigned by the teacher or the both” (Shrivastava, 2008).

Shahnawaj, (1990) had taken a study on environmental awareness and environmental attitude of secondary and higher secondary school teachers and students. In his study he has find out that girls possess significantly more awareness of the environment than boys.

Praharaj, B (1991) had taken a study on environmental knowledge, environmental attitude and perception regarding environmental education among preserves and in-service secondary school teachers. In his study he has found that the level of environmental knowledge was found low among preserves teachers although conceptual knowledge was moderate. In this study teacher perceived that environmental education could be a core part of social science and general science and science syllabus in secondary school as well as mass

media have a potential role to play in imparting environmental education.

Gopalakrishnan, S (1992) in his research paper had studied the impact of environmental education on primary school children. In her study she has found that the distribution of the total environmental education test scores of the entire sample approached the normal form while implied that studying environmental education had a very impact on the children.

Emergence of the Problem

It is a fact that human as one of the highly evolved member of the biosphere; put a serious impact on the global environment and vice versa. These adverse effects on the environment of globe act as polluting factors and invite various saviour calamities. There are various kind of environmental pollution against which environmental awareness must be increased among the human beings specially school students our future prospect for recovering the unbalanced environment.

In these respect proper research work must be done for a better balanced environment. Through environmental factors are greatly related with the living part of the nature and it is essential to study the correlation between Environmental Education and Biological Science as well as those individual subjects.

Objectives

The objectives of the study are

- To study the important factors of the environment.
- To access the impact of Environmental Studies on the secondary students.

- To access the impact of environmental awareness through a test on the secondary students.
- To determine the extent of environmental awareness among students.
- To investigate whether there is any relation between scores of the students of Environmental Awareness and achievement in Life Science.

Hypothesis

0H_1 : There exists no significant difference between mean of scores of the students of Environmental Awareness and achievement in Life Science.

0H_2 : There exists no significant correlation between scores of the students of Environmental Awareness and achievement in Life Science.

Delimitation of the Study

The present study is delimited to rural and urban Government aided schools affiliated by WBBSE of South 24 Parganas district in West Bengal. The study is delimited to the students of secondary school.

Methodology

Research methodology is very important to be accepted in the field of research, which describes the various steps of the plan to be adopted to be adopted in solving a research problem.

The method adopted according to the nature and objectives of the present study is "Descriptive Survey Method".

Population

The present study is a survey type descriptive research where 100 samples are taken strata wise (urban and rural). Four Bengali medium schools affiliated by WBBSE were selected from 24 Parganas (S) district (two from rural and two from urban) in West Bengal. Achievement in Life Science Scores of Annual Examination (class - IX) of 305 students was taken as a raw data for investigation. Among these scores 100 scores of achievement in Life Science was taken into consideration randomly. A three point scale with 25 questions was developed by the researchers about Environmental Awareness (Env. Awr.) was adopted on 100 randomly selected students of Class -X for collecting data on Environmental Awareness. Analysis of data is done with the help of statistics like mean, S.D,S.E., t- test and correlation.

Sample

Random sampling technique was adopted for the study. Randomly 100 students are taken into consideration from the entire scores (Achievement in Life Science, and Test score of Environmental Awareness).

Process of Data Collection

A questionnaire was developed based on environmental awareness skills basically on water pollution for students. The questionnaire was developed on five aspect [Table-1] of environmental awareness on water pollution. This are distributed randomly among the students. Students gives their response independently and individually of this questionnaire.

Table 1 : Different Aspect of Dimension

Sl. No.	Name of Aspects	No. of Items
1.	Knowledge on water pollution	5
2.	Understanding on Water Pollution	4
3.	Causes of Water pollution	4
4.	Remedies of Water pollution	5
5.	Extent of Awareness on water Pollution	7

Tools and Scoring Procedure

A questionnaire having 25 questions on water pollution relating to environmental awareness was developed by researcher is used in the study of data collection. The questionnaire was developed with different dimension with different aspect and it has two types of statement, one is positive point of view (Favourable items) and another is negative point of view (Unfavourable items). Out of 25 questions there are 14 favourable items and 11 unfavourable items. Among these, there are three responses for each item. The score for each item varied from 2 to 0 (2, 1, 0) for corresponding favourable items

and 0 to 2 (0, 1, 2) for corresponding unfavourable items .

Results and Discussions

The raw data collected by the test were to be tabulated, organized, analysed and interpreted for drawing sound calculations and valid generalization. The statistical methods applied for analysis of data included descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

Descriptive statistics included calculation of Mean , Standard Deviation of the tabulated data and corresponding t- values and Correlation Coefficients were calculated.

Table 3 : Statistical results

	L.Sc. Achiv.	Env.Awr.
Mean	63.04	82.03
Standard Error	1.13136184	0.556042
Median	64.5	82
Mode	53	86
Standard Deviation	11.3136184	5.560421
N	100	100

Table 2 : Responses of different aspects on water pollution

Sl. No.	Name of Aspects	Alternatives		
		YES	UNDECIDED	NO
1.	Knowledge on water pollution (500 Responses)	384 (76.8%)	7 (1.4%)	109 (21.8%)
2.	Understanding on Water Pollution (400 Responses)	253 (63.25%)	43 (10.75%)	104 (26.0%)
3.	Causes of Water pollution (400 Responses)	239 (59.75%)	20 (5.0%)	141 (35.25%)
4.	Remedies of Water pollution (500 Responses)	373 (74.6%)	26 (5.2%)	101 (20.2%)
5.	Extent of Awareness on water Pollution (700 Responses)	441 (63.0%)	85 (12.14%)	174 (24.86%)

By applying the scoring procedure mentioned above it was found the means, SD, SE of scores of the students of Environmental Awareness and achievement in Life Science are shown in table-3.

It was also found that the knowledge on water pollution is the highest percentage (76.8%) of the secondary students and Extent of awareness on water pollution is moderate [Table-2].

Table 4 : t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

Env. Awr.	L.Sc. Achiv.	
Mean	82.03	63.04
Variance	30.91828283	32.337374
Observations (N)	100	100
df	198	
t Stat (Calculated)	10.11521138	
P(T<=t) one-tail	5.90349E-20	
t Critical one-tail	1.652585784	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.1807E-19	
t Critical two-tail	1.972017432	

The computed t-values is higher than the table value of 't', so 't' is significant difference between mean of scores of the students of Environmental Awareness and Life Science [Table-4]. The null hypothesis is rejected and it can be concluded that there is a significant difference present between the variables at 5% level of significance.

On the other hand the computed coefficient of correlation is -0.015 between achievement in Life Science and score in Environmental Awareness. There exists slight / almost negligible

relationship (-0.015) between them. So the 2nd null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusions

The environmental awareness on water pollution were studied on five dimensions of aspects like knowledge, understanding, causes, remedies and extent of awareness on water pollution. The present study revealed that knowledge on water pollution is the highest percentage (76.8%) of the secondary students and Extent of awareness on water pollution is moderate in West Bengal.

From the statistical analysis it is observed that there is a significant difference present between mean of scores of the students of Environmental Awareness and Life Science at 5% level of significance. It is also found that low correlation presents between achievement in Life Science and score in Environmental Awareness.

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